

Electron spin resonance (ESR) spectroscopy study of cheese treated with accelerated electrons

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Highlights

- New data on the use of Electron Spin Resonance spectroscopy (ESR) are reported
- Only one native ESR signal was found in all types of cheese
- In irradiated cheeses, a new ESR signal is detected
- The storage time effect in free radicals accumulation and decay are studied by ESR
- ESR could be a suitable technique to detect irradiation treatments on cheese

1 **Abstract**

2 The generation, accumulation and decay of free radicals in six varieties of cheese, irradiated
3 (0–4 kGy) in an electron accelerator, have been studied by electron spin resonance (ESR)
4 spectroscopy. Remarkably, the ESR spectra of all untreated cheeses showed only one singlet signal
5 with a *g-factor* of 2.0064 ± 0.0005 . Surprisingly, the ESR spectra of irradiated samples presented a
6 new signal with *g-factor* of 2.0037 ± 0.0003 which was independent of the type of cheese, and
7 which might be due to free radicals from the radiolysis of proteins. Surface regression models ($P <$
8 0.0001) established the relationship among signal intensity, absorbed dose (0, 1, 2 and 4 kGy) and
9 storage time (0 to 180 days) for the different types of cheese. Results suggested that the analysis by
10 ESR (or electron paramagnetic resonance, EPR) is suitable to evaluate, either qualitatively or
11 quantitatively, the irradiation treatment of different types of cheese.

12

13 **Keywords:** cheese; electron spin resonance (ESR); EPR; food irradiation; food control.

14 **1. Introduction**

15 Treatment with accelerated electrons (E-beam) is a non-thermal procedure and one of the
16 available tools to increase the shelf life of several foods through the inactivation of several
17 pathogens, thus bringing on an improvement of the microbiological safety. This treatment has been
18 used in various products ready for consumption (ready-to-eat) with different antimicrobial efficacy.
19 For example, Medina et al. (2009) compared the sanitation of cold-smoked salmon by E-beam
20 irradiation and high pressure and Cambero, Cabeza, Ordoñez, & Hoz (2011) optimized the dose of
21 irradiation in mayonnaise potato salad. Directly linked to the issue of this work, the studies on the
22 inactivation of *Listeria monocytogenes* in irradiated Feta (Konteles, Sinanoglou, Batrinou, &
23 Sflomos, 2009) and in soft whey cheese (Tsiotsias, Savvaidis, Vassila, Kontominas, & Kotzekidou,
24 2002) have to be remarked. In addition, Seisa et al. (2004) analysed the effect of E-beam on
25 Cheddar and Velasco, Ordoñez, Cabeza, & Cambero (2016) demonstrated that E-beam treatment is
26 a suitable method for the inactivation of pathogens in mould cheese without alteration on texture
27 and sensory attributes at lower dose than 2 kGy.

28 Governmental regulation of food irradiation varies considerably from country to country.
29 Although there is an agreement among international committee experts that food is safe and
30 wholesome for consumption after irradiation up to a dose of 10 kGy, a common approval is still
31 pendent, and most countries approve food irradiation on a case-by-case basis. The United States
32 (US) Food and Drug Administration (FDA) regulated the food irradiation as a food additive, and
33 not as a food process, since the US Congress explicitly stated that "Sources of radiation (including
34 particle accelerators, radioactive isotopes, and X-ray machines) intended for use in processing food
35 are included in the term food additive" (Morehouse & Komolprasert, 2004). In the European Union,
36 the food irradiation regulations in several countries have been or are being harmonized through
37 compliance with the Codex General Standard for Irradiated Foods and the relevant

38 recommendations of the International Consultative Group on Food Irradiation (FAO/IAEA). In fact,
39 the framework directive of the European Parliament adopted in 1999 (EC, 1999) includes a
40 “positive list” permitting irradiation only of dried aromatic herbs, spices and vegetable seasonings;
41 and a maximum overall average of absorbed radiation dose of 10 kGy. Moreover, any Member
42 State is allowed to add a new authorisation, previously granted in another member, when the EC’s
43 Scientific Committee for Food had already documented the specific application. Nowadays,
44 Belgium, France, Italy, The Netherlands, Poland, United Kingdom and Czech Republic have
45 adopted such provisions (EC, 2009).

46 It is clear from the foregoing that the availability of analytical methods to estimate the
47 irradiation treatment applied is mandatory both to facilitate inspection and legislative controls, and
48 to contribute to consumer confidence in the technology. Recently, Zanardi, Caligiani & Novelli
49 (2018) reviewed the literature describing the last improvements that have been published related to
50 electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) or electron spin resonance (ESR), 2-alkylcyclobutanones
51 and o-tyrosine-based methods, and Metabolomics (Nuclear magnetic resonance and near infrared
52 spectroscopy coupled with chemometric tools) and Sensors (Electronic nose and Biosensors) as
53 emerging detection methods for irradiated food.

54 The spectrum of ESR (or EPR) is based on the absorption of a microwave radiation
55 produced by a transition between energy levels of unpaired electrons. With this procedure, only
56 compounds with unpaired electrons are detected without interference of other molecules. It is the
57 only available method for the direct detection of paramagnetic species (free radicals, transition
58 metal ions and bi-radicals) in biological systems (Shimoyama, Ukai, & Nakamura, 2007).
59 Therefore, it is possible its usage to assess the formation of free radicals in irradiated foods. The
60 European Union has accepted the ESR as a standard method for the detection of irradiated food
61 containing bone (EN 1786, 1996), cellulose (EN 1787, 2000) or granulated sugar (EN 13708,

62 2001). However, it has been estimated that the potential of ESR in this field is much broader. In
63 fact, our group demonstrated the utility of this spectroscopy for tracking different types of irradiated
64 dry-cured hams through the analysis of their lipid fraction (Escudero et al., 2012). **Even so, it**
65 **should not be forgotten that quantification by ESR is relative or semi-quantitative, and not absolute**
66 **on spin levels.**

67 The primary purpose of this study is to prove the usefulness of ESR (or EPR) as a tool to
68 discriminate between non-irradiated and/or irradiated samples of different types of cheese.
69 Secondly, our study of the effects of the **E-beam irradiation** on the intensity of the native and new
70 signals increases the knowledge, related to nature and structure, of the abstraction protein radicals
71 of cheese, a food matrix. Surface regression models were also established relating intensity, dose
72 and storage time of the new signal related to irradiation treatment as a tool for food control.

73

74 **2. Materials and Methods**

75 *2.1. Sample preparation and irradiation treatment*

76 Six varieties of cheese (Camembert, Emmental, Gouda, Manchego type, Brie and Cheddar)
77 were acquired from two different market places. Portions (15–20 g) of Brie and Camembert and
78 slices (20 g, 0.5 cm thick and 2.5 cm width) of Emmental, Gouda, Manchego type and Cheddar
79 were analysed in this study.

80 Samples were vacuum-packed reaching about 20 kPa in 10 × 10 cm² bags of laminated film
81 (polyamide and polyethylene, film thickness: 90 μm) with low gas permeability (O₂ and CO₂
82 transmission rates: 35 and 150 cm³/24 h m² bar, respectively). Samples were transported (less than
83 1 h) to the irradiation plant (Ionisos Sterilization S.A, Tarancón, Cuenca, Spain) in insulated
84 polystyrene boxes and irradiated with an E-beam radiation source operating at 10 MeV. The
85 radiation doses were 1, 2 and 4 kGy. Untreated samples were used as control (0 kGy).

86 Simultaneously, cellulose triacetate dosimeters were irradiated and their absorbance used to
87 calculate the absorbed dose by the samples (ASTM, 2000). Experiments were performed at room
88 temperature (20–22 °C) in triplicate. The temperature increase was less than 2 °C during treatment.
89 After irradiation, samples were stored at 4 °C until use.

90

91 2.2. ESR measurements

92 The ESR measurements were carried out on days 0, 30, 90 and 180 of storage time after
93 irradiation. Consequently, 3 vacuum-bags containing samples from 2 different commercial brands
94 × 6 cheese varieties × 4 radiation doses × 4 storage times were studied.

95 Prior to analysis, samples were frozen at –80 °C, freeze-dried and grounded using a mortar
96 to obtain a fine powder. ESR spectra were recorded on a Bruker EMX spectrometer. Samples (500–
97 600 mg) were transferred to a cylindrical ESR tube (ER221/TUB4 Bruker quartz tube with a 4 mm
98 inner diameter). Operating parameters of the ESR spectrometer (after optimization), with a HSW
99 10432 X-band resonator 9.5 GHz, were as follows: modulation frequency, 100 kHz; modulation
100 amplitude, 4.66 Gauss; frequency, 9.84 GHz; microwave power, 2 mW; centerfield, 3510 Gauss;
101 sweep width, 400 Gauss; and receiver gain, 4104; time constant, 327.68 ms; spectrum scan time,
102 655.36 s; spectrum point number, 1024; scan number, 3. The *g*-factors of all samples were
103 estimated using DPPH as standard ($g\text{-factor} = 2.0036 \pm 0.0003$) (Poole, 1996; Yordanov, 1996).

104 The signal intensity was calculated from the double integral of the ESR spectra. The
105 amplitude of the first derivative of the spectrum was taken as a measurement of the relative radical
106 concentration. The *g*-factor was calculated using the expression: $g\text{-factor} = h \cdot \nu / B_o \cdot \mu_B$ where *h* is
107 the Planck constant (6.63×10^{-34} J s), ν is the frequency (Hz), B_o is the Magnetic field (Gauss) and
108 μ_B corresponds to Bohr Magneton (9.2740×10^{-24} J/T).

109

110 2.4. Statistical analysis

111 Shapiro-Wilks test was applied to check the fit of the samples to a normal distribution (90%
112 confidence). When samples fitted the normal distribution, a one-way ANOVA analysis was
113 performed. When samples did not fit a normal distribution, Kruskal–Wallis test was used to
114 determine the null hypothesis, that the medians of the variable within each of the sample levels
115 were the same. Duncan’s test for multiple mean comparisons was applied to ascertain differences
116 among means. Simple regression analyses (using a Durbin-Watson statistics test, at a 95%
117 confidence level) were performed to determine the relationships between irradiation dose and signal
118 intensity in the ESR spectra.

119 A regression analysis was performed to estimate the response function: $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2$
120 $+ \beta_{11}X_1^2 + \beta_{22}X_2^2 + \beta_{12}X_1X_2$ where Y is the predicted response (estimated intensity values of the
121 ESR signal). $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_{11}, \beta_{22}$ and β_{12} are the estimated coefficients of the regression, representing
122 the linear, quadratic and cross-product effects of X_1 and X_2 on the response.

123 The statistical analysis was carried out using a Statgraphics Plus version 5.1. Data were
124 brought forward as the mean and the standard deviation of each treatment.

125

126 3. Results and Discussion

127 3.1. ESR spectrometry of different types of cheese

128 Figure 1A shows the ESR spectra of non-irradiated samples from the six types of cheese. As
129 it can be observed, the signals of the untreated varieties presented a similar shape, with a mean
130 value of the intensity of 1.21×10^6 a.u. ranging from 1.55×10^6 (corresponding to Manchego type) to
131 9.66×10^5 a.u. (for Cheddar) and an analogous g -factor of 2.0064 ± 0.0005 (Table 1). Thus implying
132 an independence of the radical characteristics from the type of cheese (no statistically significant
133 difference observed, $P > 0.05$).

134 Currently, the origin of native EPR signals has not been unequivocally clarified in foods yet.
135 Highly probable, they must derive from the small quantity of metal paramagnetic ions and/or the
136 stable free radicals of the organic (macro)molecules, which constitute the food matrixes. Besides,
137 depending on the phase (structural proteins, lipid components, carbohydrate compounds or aqueous
138 phase and its solubilized compounds such as vitamins, globular proteins or simple sugars), different
139 radicals could be expected. Nevertheless, the lower free water and the greater structural rigidity of
140 the matrix, the higher radical stability has been described (Taub, 1984). In fact, Stachowicz (1998)
141 reported that grinding and/or lyophilization of biological products and foods involved an increase of
142 the intensity of the related native EPR signals.

143 The value of the *g-factor* (*g*) characterises the paramagnetic centre by providing enough
144 information to distinguish among radicals centred on carbon, nitrogen or sulphur (Schaich, 1980).
145 In Fig. 1A, it is shown a singlet with $g = 2.0064 \pm 0.0005$, height peak-to-peak (ΔH_{pp}) = 10–12
146 Gauss (G) and a total spectral width of 50–60 G.

147 Attending to the present study, such ESR signal might be mainly attributed to the protein
148 component of cheese. In fact, such radical was detected in low-fat products in which the lipid
149 component could not be taken into consideration (Huvaere et al., 2011). Besides, it differs widely
150 from the radicals linked to the presence of lactose (Lee, Kwan, Ahn, & Jeong, 2010; Stapelfeldt,
151 Nielsen, Jensen, & Skibsted, 1999; Stapelfeldt, Nielsen, & Skibsted, 1997). Nevertheless, other
152 protein, lipid or inorganic radicals; although a minority group, should not be forgotten. In fact, the
153 signal showed no fine structure; therefore, several radicals might be present. Cheese matrices are
154 multicomponent systems, which were distributed into, at least, two phases. Considering such
155 complexity, it cannot be ruled out whether or not each of the observed spectra were a superposition
156 of two or more radicals. More studies would be necessary to elucidate the nature of the observed

157 native radical(s). Nevertheless, it must be underlined for both scientific and applicable fields, the
158 fact that only one signal was observed and it was independent of the type of cheese.

159

160 3.2. ESR spectrometry of irradiated cheeses

161 As it can be seen in Fig. 1B, the ESR spectra of irradiated cheeses (4 kGy) were different
162 when comparing with the spectra of the untreated (0 kGy) ones (Fig. 1A). The shape of the spectra
163 was modified by E-beam treatment since a new ESR signal appeared with a $g = 2.0037 \pm 0.0003$,
164 $\Delta H_{pp} = 16\text{--}20$ G. Remarkably, it turned to be common for all the analysed types of cheese when
165 they were irradiated within a range from 1 to 4 kGy (Figure S1). Significant differences ($P < 0.05$)
166 for the ESR signal intensity were detected depending on the type of cheese and the applied dose
167 (Table 1). The lowest ESR signal intensity ($P < 0.05$) was detected in samples of Camembert and
168 Brie cheeses (Table 1). In these types of cheese, treatments of at least 2 kGy were necessary to
169 detect the new ESR signal with a $g = 2.0037 \pm 0.0003$ (Table 1).

170 Several authors have studied by ESR the effect of the light exposure on cream cheese
171 (Kristensen, & Skibsted, 1999; Westermann, Bruggemann, Olsen, & Skibsted, 2009), semi-hard
172 cheese (Dalsgaard et al., 2010; Kristensen, Orlien, Mortensen, Brockho, & Skibsted, 2000;
173 Mortensen, Sørensen, & Stapelfeldt, 2002) and on milk powder (Lee et al., 2010; Stapelfeldt et al.,
174 1999). These studies presented similar both the *g-value* of the signals and the shape of the ESR
175 spectra to our findings on irradiated cheeses. Besides, Boatright et al. (2008) studied the E-beam
176 treatment of aminoacids, peptides and proteins by ESR in isolated soy proteins and observed similar
177 spectra, therefore similar radicals. In addition, supporting a relationship of the nature of the radicals
178 with protein structures, Seisa et al. (2004) observed different peptide profiles while comparing non-
179 irradiated and irradiated samples of Cheddar cheese. However, on authors' knowledge, such ESR
180 signal has not been characterized yet. On one hand, some authors associated an oxygen-centred

181 radical in alkoxy (Westermann et al., 2009) or in tyrosyl radicals (Huvaere et al., 2011) within a
182 peptide chain. Thus implying that, in these cases, the free radical would have been generated by
183 casein oxidations and/or by the involvement of cross-linking dityrosine precursors (Dalsgaard et al.,
184 2010). On the other hand, other authors described that such *g-values* would implicate radicals
185 centred either on nitrogen (Kristensen et al., 1999; Westermann et al., 2009) or on carbon atoms
186 (Boatright et al., 2008).

187 The free radicals produced by irradiation might engage in a number of reactions leading to
188 the formation of stable radiolytic compounds (Lee, Volkov, Byun, & Lee, 2002). Fig. 1B shows a
189 spectrum with a doublet at $g = 2.0037$ characterized by a coupling constant of 16–20 G. The slight
190 asymmetry of this signal (reflecting the interaction of the unpaired electrons with a single α -
191 hydrogen) is typical for the named “abstraction or backbone protein radical” (Taub, 1984) related to
192 aminoacids, peptides and proteins (Lee et al., 2002) whose major radiolytic reactions at room
193 temperature in vacuum involve preferential cleavages in the vicinity of the carbonyl group.

194 Lee et al. (2002) and Terryn, Deridder, Sicard–Roselli, Tilquin, & Houée–Levin (2005)
195 studied the formed radicals by γ -irradiation on soybean paste and on proteins in solid state,
196 respectively. These authors reported similar spectra to those obtained in the present study. However,
197 it has to be kept in mind that the signal has not a clear fine structure within all doses and/or storage
198 times; therefore, two or more radicals might be also present (Figure S1) and, probably, also related
199 with the evolution of the structures implied in the native signal. Therefore, it can be assumed that
200 the ESR signals detected in the irradiated cheeses correspond to radicals related to proteins.
201 According to Lee et al. (2002) and Terryn et al. (2005), plausible structures of the radicals related to
202 proteins are shown in Figure 2.

203 The effect of the absorbed dose on the signal intensity on each type of cheese is depicted in
204 Table 1 and Figure 3. **The direct analysis by ESR (unprocessed samples) does not allow obtaining**

205 an absolute quantification of the detected radicals. However, by comparing the intensity of the
206 signal it is possible to perform a spin-related analysis, for a relative or semi-quantitative
207 assessment of the formation of radicals. In all irradiated samples, the formed radical was
208 proportional to the absorbed dose. An increase ($P < 0.05$) of the intensity of the ESR signal related
209 to irradiation was observed when the absorbed dose increased at any storage time (Fig. S2). A high
210 significant positive linear regressions ($P < 0.0001$) were found between the dose (X , kGy) and the
211 intensity of the signal related to irradiation (Y , $\times 10^6$, arbitrary units) in all types of cheese:
212 Camembert ($Y = 4.43X + 0.75$, $R^2 = 0.76$), Emmental ($Y = 9.50X + 3.44$, $R^2 = 0.92$), Gouda ($Y =$
213 $10.03X + 2.01$, $R^2 = 0.85$), Manchego type ($Y = 7.78X + 1.25$, $R^2 = 0.93$), Brie ($Y = 3.68X + 1.38$, R^2
214 $= 0.72$), and Cheddar ($Y = 9.14X + 2.15$, $R^2 = 0.95$). The lowest values of correlation coefficient
215 (R^2) (0.76 – 0.72) corresponded to Camembert and Brie cheeses because in them, the ESR signal (g
216 $= 2.0037$) was only detected with E-beam treatment higher than 1 kGy (Fig. 3 and S2).

217 The evolution of the intensity of the signal with $g = 2.0037 \pm 0.0003$, during the storage time
218 of the samples at 4 °C, was shown in Fig. 3. The water content (Table S1) of the different types of
219 cheese is one of the first factors that would explain the intensity differences of the ESR signal on
220 day 0 (immediately after E-beam treatment) (Table 1 and Fig. 2), and the accumulation and decay
221 of free radicals after 30, 90 and 180 d of storage after E-beam treatment at different doses (Fig. 3
222 and S2). The higher intensity of the EPR signals, the lower moisture obtained by lyophilization was
223 observed. Thus, Emmental and Cheddar types showed lower moisture content and higher intensity
224 of the signal than the other types of cheese (Table S1 and Fig. S2). Related, Camembert and Brie
225 showed, independently of the storage time, lower intensity of the signal related to irradiation and
226 higher water content than the other cheeses (Table S1 and Fig. S2).

227 Stachowicz (1998) and Taub (1984) reported that the stability of radicals induced by
228 radiation treatment varies depending on their location, structure and moisture content. Some of

229 them decay within minutes (in wet samples) while others decay after days, weeks or even months
230 (in dry components of foods). Besides, rigid structures constrain the radical implying a kinetically
231 impaired reactivity. Thus, although a very low concentration of stabilised paramagnetic species has
232 been detected in inelastic matrixes, their abundance is high enough to be detected by ESR; such is
233 the case of irradiated bones (Stachowicz, 1998; Yarkov, Tret'yakov, & Khramov, 2000) and dry-
234 cured ham (Escudero et al., 2012). In irradiated and dried fruits, mushrooms and other foods from
235 vegetable origin, the ESR signals have been described as being unstable and decaying within a few
236 days of storage (Stachowicz, 1998). The composition of oxygen of the storage atmosphere is also
237 determinant. As a rule, the lower stability of the radicals in irradiated foods the more easily react
238 with air oxygen and hence, the rate of their decay depends strongly on the content of the air inside
239 the food as well as on food porosity. In the absence of air, some of these unstable radicals may
240 survive in food for months (Stachowicz, 1998). Regarding to our cheese samples, the vacuum-
241 package granted a low contact with air/oxygen (and atmosphere humidity) during E-beam treatment
242 and storage time. Then, it is licit to consider that the generation and development (Fig. S2) of the
243 radicals associated to the irradiation treatments ($g = 2.0037 \pm 0.0003$) could be related to cheese
244 matrix characteristics, both components and structure.

245 As it can be observed in Fig. 3, at 1 kGy dose, the highest signal intensity was observed at
246 90 d of storage in Camembert and at 30 d in the other types of cheese. Related, lower changes on
247 signal intensity were detected at 4 kGy dose. In fact, Emmental and Manchego cheeses did not
248 show any difference on signal intensity along storage time at such absorbed dose (Fig. 3 and S2). At
249 2 kGy, Brie showed a maximum at 90 d but at an earlier time was observed for the other types of
250 cheese (Fig. 3). These changes of the ESR signal intensity ($g = 2.0037 \pm 0.0003$) could support the
251 plausible hypothesis that several species or structures would be formed because of the irradiation
252 treatment but a number of transformations would lead to the more stable radical (Lee et al., 2002).

253 The obtained results suggest that, the generation, accumulation and decay of the free
254 radicals, detected by ESR (*g-factor* of 2.0037), depend on three variables: the absorbed dose, the
255 storage time and the type of cheese. As mentioned above, it is possible to establish linear
256 regressions relating absorbed dose and ESR signal intensity. To consider the effect of both the E-
257 beam treatment and the storage time on the presence of radicals in different types of cheese, the
258 estimated response surface for the intensity (peak to peak, Y) of the ESR signal, using the absorbed
259 dose (X_1) and the storage time at 4 °C (X_2) has been carried out. The regression equations are
260 reported on [Figure 4](#).

261 As it can be observed, the response surfaces showed a similar evolution of the signal
262 intensity for all types of cheese. Besides, the linear and quadratic coefficients of absorbed dose were
263 clearly higher than the related to storage time, thus suggesting that the effect of the dose was higher
264 than the storage time on the progress of the signal intensity. In other words, ESR signal related to
265 irradiation of Camembert, Brie, Cheddar, Gouda, Emmental and Manchego types of cheese, can be
266 detected along customary storage time and its intensity is highly related to dose.

267 To end, the obtained results suggest the existence of a clear difference between the spectra
268 of untreated and the irradiated cheeses (Fig. 1). In addition, it is possible to establish linear
269 relationships between dose and intensity of the ESR signals associated to irradiation treatment
270 (Table 1). Moreover, the intensity of the ESR signals is relatively stable during the storage time of
271 the cheese at 4 °C (Fig. 3). These findings would support the use of ESR spectroscopy for the
272 detection of an irradiation treatment on these products.

273 Further studies must be carried out in order to establish the nature of the radicals related to
274 both the native and the associated to irradiation treatment. It is very likely that the emerging signal
275 associated with E-beam treatment involves the formation and the evolution of various radicals
276 including the evolution of the structures related to native signal.

277

278 **4. Conclusions**

279 The Electron Spin Resonance (ESR) spectra of different types of cheeses showed a
280 characteristic singlet signal with a *g-factor* of 2.0064. This signal was considered as native radical.
281 It was independent of the type of cheese and lasted in a common storage time (0–180 d).

282 Irradiation treatment (from 1 to 4 kGy) modified the ESR spectra by appearing a new signal
283 with *g-factor* of 2.0037. A doublet (coupling with 16 – 20 Gauss) in the spectra of the irradiated
284 samples suggested a structure related to α -carbonyl radicals of free aminoacids, peptides or proteins.
285 This ESR signal was characteristic of irradiated cheeses and its intensity (but not its *g-factor*)
286 depended on the absorbed dose, the storage time and the type of cheese.

287 Linear regression models were obtained to estimate the ESR signal intensity by using the
288 absorbed dose as dependent variable. Besides, surface regression models describing the effect of
289 dose and storage time on signal intensity for each type of cheese were proposed as a tool for global
290 monitoring of irradiation treatment.

291 These results point out the suitability of the analysis by ESR (or electron paramagnetic
292 resonance, EPR) to evaluate the irradiation treatment of different types of cheese.

293

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297

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397 Figure Captions:

398 Figure 1: ESR spectroscopy of different type of cheese: A) untreated samples (dose 0 kGy), B)
399 irradiated samples (dose 4 kGy).

400

401 a.u.: arbitrary units

402

403 Figure 2. Proposed structures¹ for main radicals formed by the effect of the E-Beam treatment on
404 the matrix of several types of cheese.

405

406 ¹ Considering the studies of Lee et al. (2002) and Terryn et al. (2005) in different protein
407 compounds.

408

409 Figure 3. Accumulation and decay of the radicals (considering the intensity of the ESR signal)
410 detected in treated cheeses with E-beam at different doses (1, 2 and 4 kGy) along storage time (0,
411 30, 90 and 180 d).

412

413 ¹ $\times 10^6$; a.u.: arbitrary units.

414 Different letters within the same dose and type of cheese, imply statistical difference in the intensity
415 along storage time ($P < 0.05$).

416

417 Figure 4. Response surfaces showing the relationship of signal intensity ($g = 2.0037 \pm 0.0003$),
418 absorbed dose and storage time of different types of cheese treated with E-beam.

419 R^2 = determination coefficient; R^{2*} = adjusted determination coefficient; SE = standard error for the
420 estimated; Y = intensity of the signal related to irradiation, $\times 10^6$, (a.u.) arbitrary units; X_1 =
421 absorbed dose, kGy; X_2 = storage time, days.

Table 1: Apparent yields of radicals detected by ESR in different types of cheese before a)¹ and immediately after E-beam treatment b)² at different doses (0, 1, 2 and 4 kGy).

Dose	Camembert	Emmental	Gouda	Manchego	Brie	Cheddar
a)						
0	13 ± 3.2 ^β	10 ± 2.5 ^β	12 ± 5.4 ^β	28 ± 7.2 ^α	13 ± 4.2 ^β	10 ± 4.6 ^β
b)						
0	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
1	n.d	16 ± 5.2 ^{c,α}	0.7 ± 0.2 ^{b,β}	0.4 ± 0.2 ^{c,β}	n.d	10 ± 4.1 ^{b,α}
2	15 ± 1.2 ^δ	26 ± 4.7 ^{b,β}	34 ± 6.3 ^{a,α}	19 ± 3.3 ^{b,γ}	10 ± 2.9 ^δ	19 ± 5.1 ^{b,γ}
4	17 ± 2.8 ^β	41 ± 5.2 ^{a,α}	39 ± 5.3 ^{a,α}	34 ± 6.9 ^{a,α}	18 ± 1.6 ^β	35 ± 2.3 ^{a,α}

¹ESR signal intensity (peak to peak)³ *g-factor* 2.0067 ± 0.0005: native signal.

²ESR signal intensity (peak to peak)³ *g-factor* 2.0037 ± 0.0003: irradiated signal.

³arbitrary units, ×10⁵.

In table 1b, different letters (a,b,c...) within the same column indicate significant difference (P < 0.05) for the E-beam treatment (dose effect)

In Table 1a and 1b, different letters (α, β, γ...) within the same row indicate significant difference (P < 0.05) among types of cheese.

n.d no signal detected

Figure 1.

1. A

1. B

Figure 2.

Figure 3

Figure 4

a) Camembert

$$Y = -2.56 + 8.07X_1 + 0.072X_2 - 0.547X_1^2 - 0.00033X_2^2 - 0.016X_1X_2$$

[$P < 0.005$, $R^2 = 0.80$, $R^{2*} = 0.75$; SE = 4.517]

b) Emmental

$$Y = 1.89 + 15.9X_1 - 0.01X_2 - 1.43X_1^2 - 0.00005X_2^2 - 0.0066X_1X_2$$

[$P < 0.0001$, $R^2 = 0.97$, $R^{2*} = 0.95$; SE = 3.232]

c) Gouda

$$Y = -2.93 + 16.32X_1 + 0.149X_2 - 1.25X_1^2 - 0.00084X_2^2 - 0.015X_1X_2$$

[$P < 0.0001$, $R^2 = 0.91$, $R^{2*} = 0.86$; SE = 6.213]

d) Manchego type

$$Y = -1.83 + 11.19X_1 + 0.049X_2 - 0.731X_1^2 - 0.0002X_2^2 - 0.0051X_1X_2$$

[$P < 0.0001$, $R^2 = 0.94$, $R^{2*} = 0.91$; SE = 3.606]

e) Brie

$$Y = -2.189 + 9.32X_1 + 0.045X_2 - 1.16X_1^2 - 0.0001X_2^2 - 0.017X_1X_2$$

[$P < 0.001$, $R^2 = 0.82$, $R^{2*} = 0.73$; SE = 3.288]

f) Cheddar

$$Y = -1.41 + 12.63X_1 + 0.059X_2 - 0.942X_1^2 - 0.00026X_2^2 + 0.0055X_1X_2$$

[$P < 0.0001$, $R^2 = 0.98$, $R^{2*} = 0.98$; SE = 2.219]

Supplementary Material

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Supplementary Material

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Supplementary Material

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